

Amperometric Estimation of La^{3+} and Ce^{3+} with Cupferron using d.m.e.

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Cupferron has been employed as a reagent for the amperometric titrations of La^{3+} and Ce^{3+} in very dilute solution using d.m.e. Hydrochloric acid ($\text{pH}=2.75$) has been used as supporting electrolyte. These titrations revealed cupferron to metal ratio of 1:1. Titrations are not hampered by the presence of a fairly large amount of Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ , Mg^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , NO_2^- , NO_3^- , CH_3COO^- and ClO_4^- ions. Furthermore, micro and ultramicro quantities of La^{3+} and Ce^{3+} have been successfully determined with an error of less than $\pm 0.70\%$.

CUPFERRON, an ammonium salt of N-nitroso-phenyl hydroxylamine [$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}(\text{NO})\text{ONH}_4$] was introduced as a precipitant for Cu^{2+} and Fe^{3+} . The reagent has been successfully used in the determination of metals, such as those belonging to titanium family¹. Kolthoff and Liberti² have amperometrically titrated Cu^{2+} ion with cupferron using d.m.e. as an indicator electrode. The amperometric titration of yttrium and some other rare earths using a rotating platinum anode and stationary platinum cathode in an ammoniacal acetate medium of pH 3.5 to 6, has been reported by Vasilenko³. The use of cupferron in the amperometric titrimetry of various other ions e.g. Fe^{3+} , Tl^{3+} , Sn^{4+} , Pr^{3+} and Nd^{3+} has been discussed in the literature. No account, however, is available in literature on the use of cupferron as a reagent for amperometric titration of La^{3+} and Ce^{3+} on a d.m.e.

The results of amperometric titrations of La^{3+} and Ce^{3+} with cupferron on a d.m.e. at $\text{pH}=2.75 \pm 0.01$ are reported in the present paper.

Experimental

Cupferron (B.D.H.) was purified⁴ by recrystallisation from ethanol. The dried crystals were stored in dark over ammonium carbonate. A fresh solution of this reagent was prepared in air free distilled water before use and the solution was standardised by amperometric titration method⁵. La^{3+} and Ce^{3+} solutions were prepared by dissolving a calculated amount of $\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ [Riedel] and $\text{CeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ [Fluka], respectively in the required volume of double distilled water. The solutions were standardised by conventional titrimetric method⁶.

Hydrochloric acid ($\text{pH}=2.75$) was used as a supporting electrolyte for the study of the polarographic behaviour of cupferron and purified nitrogen gas was passed through the solutions before recording the polarograms. A manual polaro-

graphic set up with multiflex galvanometer (sens = 8.10×10^{-9} amp/div) was used for measurement of current. The d.m.e. used in conjunction with S.C.E. had the characteristics $m=2.45$ mg/sec, $t=2.5$ sec/drop and $h=43.5$ cm.

For titrations, a number of solutions containing calculated amounts of La^{3+} and Ce^{3+} (0.005 mM to 0.05 mM) were prepared. The pH of these solutions was adjusted at 2.75 with hydrochloric acid. Titrations of these solutions were carried out at an applied voltage of -1.20 volts (vs S.C.E.) using an H-type cell with d.m.e. as an indicator electrode and S.C.E. as reference electrode.

Results and Discussion

Cupferron gives a well defined cathodic wave in hydrochloric acid¹⁰. The half wave potential varies with pH . The height of the diffusion current is proportional to the concentration of cupferron. The plateau potential of the polarogram for cupferron, i.e. -1.20V (vs S.C.E.) (at which La^{3+} or Ce^{3+} do not give any diffusion current) was applied. The metal ion solution in dil. HCl ($\text{pH}=2.75$) was taken in a titration cell and the solution was titrated against cupferron ($\text{pH}=2.75$). After each addition of an aliquot of the titrant the galvanometer reading was noted. On plotting galvanometer reading against the titrant volume a reversed L shaped curve was observed (Fig. 1). The end point has been located graphically as the point of intersection of the two straight lines. This estimates the metal to cupferron ratio of 1:1 (Tables 1 and 2). The literature, however, records 1:3 stoichiometric ratio of metal (La^{3+} or Ce^{3+}) to cupferron. The observed 1:1 ratio may be attributed to the relatively low pH value of the test solution^{7,11}.

Similar results were observed by choosing metal as titrant and the rare earth as titrate under the identical experimental conditions. In this case an L shaped curve was observed.

TABLE 1—AMPEROMETRIC DETERMINATION OF La³⁺ WITH CUPFERRON
pH=2.75 ± 0.01

Amount of La ³⁺ taken (mM)	Amount of Cupferron consumed (mM)	Mole ratio M : L	% error
0.005	0.005	1 : 1	—
0.010	0.010	1 : 1	—
0.015	0.0140	1 : 0.993	-0.70
0.020	0.020	1 : 1	—
0.025	0.0249	1 : 0.996	-0.40
0.030	0.0298	1 : 0.993	-0.70
0.040	0.0401	1 : 1.0025	+0.25
0.050	0.05	1 : 1	—

TABLE 2—AMPEROMETRIC DETERMINATION OF Ce³⁺ WITH CUPFERRON ; pH=2.75 ± 0.01

Amount of La ³⁺ taken (mM)	Amount of Cupferron consumed (mM)	Mole ratio M : L	% error
0.005	0.00503	1 : 1.0060	+0.60
0.010	0.010	1 : 1	—
0.015	0.01492	1 : 0.9946	-0.54
0.020	0.0201	1 : 0.9950	-0.50
0.025	0.025	1 : 1	—
0.030	0.0302	1 : 1.0067	+0.67
0.040	0.040	1 : 1	—
0.050	0.0502	1 : 1.004	+0.40

The data in Tables 1 and 2 clearly indicate that the method is successfully applicable for the estimation of micro and ultramicro quantities of the metal ions under study with an error of less than ±0.70%.

Effect of diverse ions : Concentrated solutions of the diverse ions used were prepared. For interference studies, known amount of diverse ion was added to a definite amount of metal ion and the

pH was adjusted to 2.75 using dil HCl solution. The solution was titrated against cupferron amperometrically as described above. Titrations are not in any way hampered by the presence of different amount of the diverse ions (Table 3). Moreover,

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS ON THE AMPEROMETRIC DETERMINATION OF La³⁺ AND Ce³⁺

Metal taken : La³⁺=0.01 mM(1.3891 mg), Ce³⁺=0.01 mM(1.4012 mg)

Diverse ion added	La ³⁺ found (mg)	% error	Ce ³⁺ found (mg)	% error
K ⁺ (130 mg)	1.3920	+0.20	1.3937	-0.58
Na ⁺ (115 mg)	1.3781	-0.79	1.4086	+0.58
Al ³⁺ (67 mg)	1.3854	-0.26	1.3929	-0.59
Mg ²⁺ (60 mg)	1.3782	-0.78	1.4106	+0.67
Li ⁺ (35 mg)	1.4015	+0.89	1.3950	-0.44
Zn ²⁺ (16 mg)	1.3804	-0.62	1.4185	+1.28
Cr ³⁺ (7 mg)	1.4058	+1.20	1.3851	-1.15

Figures within parenthesis indicate the maximum amount of foreign ion which do not interfere under the experimental condition.

a fairly large amount of the ions Cl⁻, I⁻, NO₃⁻, NO₂⁻, SO₄²⁻, CH₃COO⁻ is tolerated. However, neither of these two rare earths could be estimated in presence of each other. It is also found that Cu²⁺, Fe³⁺, MnO₄⁻, Ti⁴⁺, Pr³⁺ and Nd³⁺, even in small amount, interfere seriously.

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